

Impendent of the study of vocational education in vocational secondary schools in the city of Aqaba from the point of view of students

Raid Mohammad JumahAwad Al –Kderat, (PhD)

Department of Planning

Directorate of Education for Aqaba, Ministry of Education, The Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan

Raid_jo2002@yahoo.co.uk

Abstract:

The study aims to explore the impendent of the study of vocational education in vocational secondary schools in the city of Aqaba from the point of view of students know how positive and an overview of the local community of the city of Aqaba. This study is an exploratory, analytical study and follows the approach of collecting and analyzing data to draw conclusions. The researcher used the arithmetic mean, standard deviation, T-test and ANOVA test to measure the level of importance for the study questions. The study targeted a sample of members of a community of (94) students Survey, distributed to the members of the sample, the study founded the gap between secondary technical and technological campus within the comprehensive reform processors in the context of the educational system, including the correction of both educational tracks through specific training for students.

Keywords:

Vocational Education, Secondary Schools, Aqaba, Jordan

Citation:

Al –Kderat, Raid Mohammad JumahAwad (2019); Impendent of the study of vocational education in vocational secondary schools in the city of Aqaba from the point of view of students; Journal of Social Sciences (COES&RJ-JSS), Vol.8, No.3, pp:418-433; <https://doi.org/10.25255/jss.2019.8.3.418.433>.

Introduction

The modern societies inbuilt largely on the development of human resources and development in quantity and continuously, and therefore has been embraced vocational education, which means the preparation of skilled workers in basic levels of work employee occupies a prominent and distinct within the formal and non-formal educational systems, in most parts of the world, the urgent need for qualified manpower provides different areas of the labor market in the various economic sectors (Altamony and Gharaibeh, 2017; Jawabreh, 2017a; Jawabreh, et al., 2018).

Vocational education has a substantial role in the preparation of the workforce are qualified to deal with modern technology is able to cope with the rapid changes and their reflections on the nature of the needs of the labor market and the changing of professions and skills, prompting States, particularly developed countries, to introduce radical reforms in this sector through the integration of technical and vocational secondary education programs higher education with the needs of the labor market and secure with the scientific and cultural changes and social transformations the vocational and technical education system suffers from many constraints, limited the evolution, and kept the various community segments in the running for the sweating, reflect this negatively on its contribution to the growth and development of the components of the national economy (Abu Rumman et al., 2013; Adele, 2000; Alananzeh et al., 2018; Al-Hussein, 2015; ALSarayreh, 2011).

According to a report prepared by the Higher Population Council (HPC), the overall ratio of students enrolled in vocational and technical training programmers stood at 17.5 percent in 2011, 17.7 percent in 2012 and 17 percent in 2013.

The study to conduct periodic surveys to the labor market needs of skills in different professional disciplines and areas, and follow-up of graduates. The establishment of effective partnership with the private sector for the financing of vocational education and training. In addition to the preparation of professional education programs and improve society's view of vocational education. The percentage of technical and vocational graduates in the Jordanian labor market stood at 14.2 percent in 2013, the HPC showed (Abu Rumman et al., 2013; Adele, 2000; Alananzeh et al, 2018; Al-Hussein, 2015; ALSarayreh, 2011).

Jordan has established many of the institutions to study, recommend, regulate, monitor and intervene to maintain and improve education at the primary, secondary, vocational, and technical and university levels. These institutions include the following:

1. Ministry of Education (primary, secondary, vocational, technical)
2. Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research (Community Colleges, Universities)
3. Ministry of Labour (Vocational Training Centers)
4. Center of Accreditation and Quality Assurance (CAQA) – (Primary, Secondary and Vocational Education)
5. Higher Education Accreditation Council (HEAC) – (community colleges, universities)
6. ETVET Fund – Linkages between employers and providers of technical and vocational education and training.
7. NCHRD – Studies and recommendations human resource development requirements to achieve socioeconomic needs
8. QRTA – Queen Rania Teacher Academy – Training and certification of Teachers

Background study

The Vocational Training Corporation (VTC) has been calling on the private sector to lead vocational training programmers, as it is the main employer of their graduates.

The Education Ministry has been cooperating with the Labour Ministry and the VTC to encourage students to enroll in vocational training programmes, enabling students to pursue their technical diplomas, without having to apply to the Tawjihi (Jawabreh and Al Sarayreh, 2017; Jawabreh et al., 2015; Jawabreh et al., 2017).

In the past, Jordan's public education and training authorities engaged only very little with skills demands in the labor market or with social partners. However, over the past half-decade or so the government and ETVET authorities have taken tangible, if incomplete, steps to engage with the social partners, who have also begun to treat ETVET policies as a priority. Jordan has been moving towards a tripartite system of industrial relations as part of a national strategy to develop a knowledge-based economy and society with improved education, training and skills supply, and a National Employment Strategy has been adopted for 2011–20. Jordan's labour market shows growth with job creation, yet unemployment remains obstinately high, in part as a result of inward migration of labor (Qusay et al., 2018; Anja, 1997; Ardith, 2012; Christine and Tom, 2000).

Technical education in Jordan is provided in 51 community colleges, of which 26 are public colleges offering two-year diplomas. These include 14 community colleges under Al Balqaa' University, 6 sponsored by the Armed Forces Department of Education, and 6 other governmental community colleges. Many of the colleges also offer Bachelor's degrees, where a number of students bridge the gap from community colleges to public universities. About 1,000 students have passed community college exams and have applied to make the transition into universities for the academic year 2013/14 (Sheu et al., 2004; Simon and Megginson, 1996; Simon et al., 2015; Yana et al., 2006). The preference for university education is strong in Jordan, as reflected in the low rates of community college enrolment. While national policies have emphasized the importance of community colleges playing a more important role in technical and applied fields of education in order to increase the efficiency and productivity of the labor market, the response has been slow.

In Jordan, the educational system is generally isolated from the economy. As such, the educational system is conceptualized and managed as an independent silo. Economic sectors are also generally managed as isolated silos. Thus, there is little interaction between local economic sectors and education, particularly at the school (secondary) level and vocational training levels. There is a need to help facilitate an understanding of the linkages between STEM competencies with general learning, technical education, vocational education, university education and fundamental economic requirements. Few Jordanians understand the strong linkages between STEM and learning ability with sustainable competitiveness. Thus despite the prevalence of numerous national institutions tasked with education, vocational/technical training, employment and national economic development, their linkages with the national economy and the private sector are weak. The weak linkages are because most Jordanian businesses are micro, small and medium enterprises, individually and collectively unable to identify their skill needs and requirements. As such, the vocational academic stream believes that the mathematics and physics/science literacy is generally poor for those wishing to enter the vocational secondary stream (Felix, 2008; Durden and Yang, 2006; Irina et al., 2018; Jacky and Lumby, 2000; Jawabreh, 2014).

Professional standards are used in the design of vocational and technical education and training, as well as design professional performance tests and examinations and certification level licenses to practice. The professional standards also can be used in the selection and employment of workers in enterprises, and their responsibilities and functions and relationships with other workers. And contribute to professional standards in the design of wage policies and requirements of the transition from one job to another (Jawabreh, 2017b&c; Jeremy et al., 1999; Kenneth, 1976; Lenita and Taina, 2015; Liza et al., 2015; Marlise, 2010; Martin, 1997; Martinus, 1997; Mike, 1999; Mike and Dimitrios, 2004).

In the light of this seems to be a need to develop professional standards for professions and business are common at the Arab level in the areas of industrial, construction and service, with the investment results of the classification and description of the new normative Arab Classification. The such as this effort contribute actively, as is clear in supporting the elements of coordination and liaison between the operating services and productive institutions and systems of rehabilitation, education, training and human resources development.

The hypotheses of the study

The first hypothesis: There is no positive impact among the local community look to study the specialty Hotels Management and students (female) to study the specialization of the chain."

The second hypothesis: There is no positive impact among the local community look to study the specialty Hotels Management and Students (male) to study the specialization of the chain."

The third assumption: There are no statistically significant differences attributable to the sex variable members of the study sample from the local community to work in the hotel sector."

The fourth premise: What degree of positive Community looks to study the specialization of the management of hotels? "

The fifth hypothesis: What degree of positive community looks at the work of the children in the hotel sector?"

The discussion of results

The following are the conclusions reached in accordance with the study questions:

The results of the first question the first hypothesis that emerged in which reads:

"There is a positive impact among the local community look to study the specialty Hotels Management applications (females) to study the specialization of chain at the level of significance ($\alpha \leq 05$).

To answer this question and test his hypothesis has been calculating the correlation coefficient between the community and the enthusiasm of the students to study for the management of hotels.

Table 1.The arithmetic average Standard Deviation, correlation coefficient

The Relationship	Pearson correlation coefficient	The level of significance	The arithmetic average	The Standard Deviation
An overview of the community	0.33	035, 0	13.7	2.8
Study the management of hotels			2.8	, 079

Table 1a positive correlation between the community and the turnout of female students to study the management of hotels by pearson link factor by (0.33) at the level of significance ($\alpha \leq 05$), The researcher has to make sure that the rejection of the zero hypothesis and accept the

Impendent of the study of vocational education in vocational secondary schools....

existence of 23,900 moral link between the community and the Iqbal of female students to study the hotels management at the level of significance ($\alpha \leq 05$.), the analysis of the unilateral variation t-test.

Table 2. The results of the analysis of the unilateral variance (ANOVA) of the relationship between the community and the enthusiasm of the students to study the management of hotels

The source of the Variance	The total boxes	Degrees of Freedom	The average The boxes	The value of the P	The Level The Significance
The Gradient	2.83	1	2.835	85.4	0.02
The amount of error	56.28	91	0.509		
The total	59.11	92	----		

The results of table 2 indicate the possibility of rejecting the hypothesis "there is not a positive impact among the local community and the enthusiasm of the students to study hotel management at the level of ($\alpha \leq 05$.)". There is no moral linked between the local community and the enthusiasm of the students to study the management of hotels," where the value of p tabular (3.94), which is less than the calculated value referred to in the table (85.4) No statistically significant differences indicate they are intimately related.

Table 3. The results of the t v-test, the relationship between the community and the enthusiasm of the students to study the management of hotels

The Model	Non-standard transactions		The value of the T	The Level The Significance
	The standard error	B		
Drive	0.39	1.972	5.01	0.02
An overview of the community	0.013	0.06	2.14	

The results of table 3 to reject the zero hypothesis", there is no positive impact between the community and the enthusiasm of the students to study hotel management at the level of ($\alpha \leq 05$.)). There is no moral linked between them where the value of (t) calculated (5, 01) at the level of significance (0, 035) is less than (0, 05(any reject the zero hypothesis and accept the alternative, there is a positive mental link.

The results of the second question the second hypothesis that emerged in which reads:

"There is a positive impact among the local community look to study the specialty Hotels Management Students (male) to study the specialization of chain at the level of significance ($\alpha \leq 05$)."

To answer this question and test his hypothesis has been calculating the correlation coefficient between the community and the enthusiasm of the students to study for the management of hotels. Table 4 shows the parameter link intermediate calculation.

Table 4. Pearson correlation coefficient between the community and the enthusiasm of the students to study for the management of hotels Intermediate Calculations

The Relationship	Pearson correlation coefficient	The level of significance	The arithmetic average	The Standard Deviation
An overview of the community	0.40	310,	13.7	29,
Iqbal students to study the management of hotels			3.53	, 90

Table 4a positive correlation between the community and the turnout of students to study the management of hotels by Pearson correlation coefficient (0.40) at the level of significance ($\alpha \leq 05$), Which is higher than the correlation coefficient between the community and the enthusiasm of the students to study the management of hotels. The two researchers to make sure that the rejection of the zero hypothesis and accept the existence of 23,900 moral link between the community and the Iqbal students to study hotel management at the level of significance ($\alpha \leq 05$), The analysis of the unilateral variance ANOVA and test (t).

Table 5. The results of the analysis of the unilateral variation (AVONA) the relationship between the community and the enthusiasm of the students to study the management of hotels

The source of the Variance	The total boxes	Degrees of Freedom	The average The boxes	The value of the P	The Level The Significance
The Gradient	4.928	1	4.928	6.389	0.031
The amount of error	70.191	91	.771		
The total	75.118	92	----		

The results of table 5 indicate the possibility of rejecting the hypothesis "there is not a positive impact among the local community and the enthusiasm of the students to study hotel management at the level of ($\alpha \leq 05$).". There is no moral linked between the local community and the enthusiasm of the students to study the management of hotels," where the initial value of p seriously (3.94), which is less than the calculated value referred to in the table (38.6) No statistically significant differences indicate they are intimately related.

Impendent of the study of vocational education in vocational secondary schools....

Table 6. The results of the t-test the relationship between the community and the enthusiasm of the students to study the management of hotel

The Model	Non-standard transactions		The value of the T	The Level The Significance
	The standard error	B		
Drive	0.039	2.451	5.57	0.031
An overview of the community	0.031	0.079	2.53	

Table 7. Built arithmetic averages of the standard deviations of the study questions

Paragraph No.	The arithmetic average for males	The standard deviation for males	The arithmetic average mutilation	The standard deviation of mutilation
7	4.35	1.06	4.46	.646
8	3.97	.977	4.04	.773
9	3.78	1.18	3.88	.816
10	3.41	1.17	3.62	.983
11	3.60	1.15	3.50	1.30
12	3.94	1.14	4.00	1.09
13	4.00	1.09	4.50	.707
14	3.15	1.23	2.96	1.46
15	3.84	1.01	4.00	.748
16	3.47	1.34	3.50	1.39
17	3.06	1.38	3.27	1,185
18	4.22	.975	3.92	1.016
19	3.87	1.02	3.96	.99
20	2.12	1.08	2.54	1.03
24	3.54	1.11	4.00	.938

The results of table 6 to reject the zero hypothesis", there is no positive impact between the community and the enthusiasm of the students to study hotel management at the level of ($\alpha \leq 05$). There is no moral linked between them where the value of t) calculated (57.5) at the level of an indication (0,031) is less than (0.05)(any reject the zero hypothesis and accept the alternative, there is a positive mental link.

There were no statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha \leq 05$). (Attributable to the sex variable members of the study sample from the local community in the Iqbal children to work in the hotel sector."

To answer this question and test his hypothesis was the extraction of the arithmetic average of responses of the sample study in the mindset Iqbal children to work in the hotel sector.

Table 7 shows the existence of virtual teams in the arithmetic averages standard deviations of responses of the sample study in the mindset Iqbal children to work in the hotel sector. Where the results of the arithmetic average females arithmetic averages for males of most of the paragraphs.

To make sure the differences according to the Tables 8 - The researcher has resorted to test t-test).

Table 8. Arithmetic averages of the standard deviations of the two sets of male and female members of the sample study in the mindset Iqbal children to work in the hotel sector.

Gender	The number paragraphs	Average	The Standard Deviation	The average standard error
Females	23	55.5	6.10	1.3
Male	65	54.0	6.61	83, 0

Table 9 .The degree of freedom T-test in the hotel sector

The degree of freedom	T the value of	The level of significance
22	4.30	0.01
64		

The results of table 9 indicate the possibility of refusal of the proposition that "there are no statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha \leq 0.05$), attributable to the sex variable members of the sample study in the mindset Iqbal children to work in the hotel sector." Where the Tabular trend value (support), which is less than the calculated value referred to in the table (30.4) No statistically significant differences this means that females have a positive look at the top of the male mindset Iqbal children to work in the hotel sector. To answer this question, arithmetic averages were calculated of questioner directed to study the community to study the children allocated to the management of hotels.

Table 10. Arithmetic averages and standard deviations that positive community looks to study the children allocated to the management of hotels

N	Items	Arithmetic averages	The Standard Deviation	
1	I want to study for the management of hotels.	3.05	1.11	Medium
2	I want to examine one of my sons of males allocate Hotels Management.	3.53	Were Down 0.90	High

Impendent of the study of vocational education in vocational secondary schools....

3	I want to examine one of my sons of females allocate Hotels Management.	2.79	.797	Low
4	The decision to study for the management of hotels depend in stereotype our community	3.57	1.21	High
5	Affect the religious factor to take the decision to study for the management of hotels	3.0	1.26	Mediu m
6	English language is considered an obstacle to my studies for the management of hotels.	3.13	1.32	Mediu m
21	Positive sighted students who are studying the management of hotels.	3.82	1.11	High
	The total	22.13	3.55	

The results indicate in table (4.14) that the arithmetic average (22.13) Total is the standard deviation (3.55) and also notes that the highest average my paragraph "positive sighted students who are studying Hotels Management" (3, 8) and the lowest average my paragraph " i want to examine one of my sons of females allocate Hotels Management" (2, 79).

The results of question 5 the fifth hypothesis that emerged in which reads:

"What degree of positive community looks at the work of the children in the hotel sector?"

To answer this question, arithmetic averages were calculated of questioner directed to study the community of the work of the children in the hotel sector. The results were as follows:

The results

Granting each of the trainer and the trainee high professional expertise in the field of maintenance of equipment and spare parts manufacturing in demand in the local market which is reflected positively upon entry to the labor market as unskilled workers. Providing financial returns, some of which can be used to improve the existing training equipment and machines in the industrial schools or replacement parts that can be eroded by the repeated use of the limitation period (Lam, et al., 2008; Nick et al., 1995; Nikitas and Dimitris, 1997). The echo of a wide media has an impact on the changing view of society to vocational education to the level of fine dining, which it deserves.

To contribute to bridging or bridging the gap between secondary technical and technological campus within the comprehensive reform processors in the context of the educational system, including the correction of both educational tracks through specific training for students, believes that the education system is integral to all phases of the types and levels of knowledge or regulatory requirements, however, according to the .and secondary technical and technological campus are complementary with each other in a strategic perspective and that there is a shared responsibility between the technical secondary education and technological university bridging and bridging the gap between linkages between industrial school of the Art Institute or university. The exchange of experience between university education and vocational education and the labor market. To identify outstanding students and highlight individual differences in skills to innovation and creativity.

Also, researchers called for more research on the enabling factors of applying electronic services (e.g. Masa'deh, et al., 2008, 2013a, 2013b; Karajeh and Maqableh, 2014; Maqableh and Karajeh, 2014; Al-Dmour et al., 2015; Almajali and Maqableh, 2015; Kateb et al., 2015; Maqableh et al., 2015; Masa'deh, 2016a, b; Tarhini et al., 2015; 2016, 2017a, 2017b; Almajali and Al-Dmour, 2016; Almajali et al., 2016; Alenezi et al., 2017; Aldmour et al., 2017a, b; Khwaldeh et al., 2017; Mikkawi and Al-Lozi, 2017; Obeidat et al., 2017; Yassien and Mufleh, 2017; Tarhini et al., 2018; Al-Dmour et al., 2019; Masa'deh, et al., 2019a, b; Obeidat et al., 2019), hence, future research is vital to explore in new electronic venues serving the vocational education in a better way.

Identify the normal sequence when trainees acquired skills before attending the training institutions and to accelerate developed using the mechanism proposed by our study of these .directing trainees toward knowledge exchange work "Preceding" mean?, educational and social. To contribute to the application of these in experience the relationship between the family and the school social, educational, professional or technical education or technological advances, depending on the economic side, the members of the family, educational and work "Preceding" mean?

The promotion of cultural and societal values and integrate them into the comprehensiveness in the school environment, and the emphasis on showing a clear understanding of the schools and the community cultural influences that affect it, community values and beliefs that contribute to enrich the educational process of learning (Omar et al., 2018; Petya et al., 2015; Ray and Thorogood, 1982; Richard et al., 2016; Lee et al., 2000).

Jordan lacks a coherent set of arrangements and incentives to encourage skills upgrading by employers in either the formal or the informal sector. The focus has been placed on initial VET and training to reach disadvantaged and other specific target groups. Although these programmers do not target the upgrading of existing employees' skills, the VTC does organize some upgrading programmers for employed people based on special needs expressed by companies. A recent survey found that Jordan's companies were ranked among the lowest in Arab countries as providers of training for their employees: the percentages of companies training existing employees and new hires are 38% and 47% respectively; the private sector, have little delegated responsibility to take local management decisions that involve undertaking initiatives, forming local partnerships or responding to local demands from the labor market and society at large. The national framework for financial and human resource development and for establishing and equipping training providers currently leaves little room for local initiative.

References

Abu Rumman, M., Jawabreh, O., Alhyasat, K., & Husam, H. (2013). The impact of work environment on the average of job turnover in five-star hotels in Al-aqaba city. *Business Management and Strategy*, 4(2).<https://doi.org/10.5296/bms.v4i2.402>.

Adele Ladkin, (2000). Vocational education and food and beverage experience: issues for career development. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 12(4), 226-233, <https://doi.org/10.1108/09596110010330723>.

Alananzeh, O., Al-Badarnah, M., Al-Mkhadmeh, A., & Jawabreh, O. (2018). Factors influencing MICE tourism stakeholders' decision making: the case of Aqaba in Jordan. *Journal of*

Impendent of the study of vocational education in vocational secondary schools....

Convention & Event Tourism. *Journal of Convention & Event Tourism*, 19(2), <https://doi.org/10.1080/15470148.2018.1526152>

Alananzeh, O., Masa'deh, R., Jawabreh, O., Al-Mahmoud, A., & Hamada, R. (2018). The impact of customer relationship management on tourist satisfaction: the case of Radisson Blue Resort in Aqaba city. *Journal of Environmental Management and Tourism*, 2(26), 227-240.

Al-Dmour, R., Al Haj Dawood, E., Al-Dmour, H., & Masa'deh, R. (2019). The effect of customer lifestyle patterns on the use of mobile banking applications in Jordan. *Int. J. Electronic Marketing and Retailing*, Forthcoming.

Aldmour, R., Hammdan, F., Dmour, H., Alrowwad, A., & Khwaldeh, S. (2017a). The effect of lifestyle on online purchasing decision for electronic services: the Jordanian flying e-tickets case. *Asian Social Science*, 13(11), 157-169.

Aldmour, R., Masa'deh, R., & Obeidat, B. (2017b). Factors influencing the adoption and implementation of HRIS applications: are they similar. *International Journal of Business Innovation and Research*, 14(2), 139-167.

Al-Dmour, R., Obeidat, B., & Almajali, D. (2015). The practice of HRIS applications in business organizations in Jordan: an empirical study. 4th Scientific & Research Conference on New Trends in Business, Management and Social Sciences (COES&RJ-TK15/1).

Alenezi, H., Tarhini, A., Alalwan, A., & Al-Qirim, N. (2017). Factors affecting the adoption of e-government in Kuwait: a qualitative study. *Electronic Journal of e-Government*, 15(2), 84-102.

Al-Hussein, M., Jawabreh, O., Alananzeh, O., & Ali, M. (2015). The impact of understanding the behavior of workers on the success of management, (a case study of five star hotels in Aqaba). *Journal of Management Research*, 7(3), 51-70, <https://doi.org/10.5296/jmr.v7i3.7115>.

Almajali, D., & Al-Dmour, R. (2016). The role of information technology in motivating students to accept e-learning adoption in universities: a case study in Jordanian universities. *Journal of Business & Management (COES&RJ-JBM)*, 4(1), 36-46.

Almajali, D., & Maqableh, M. (2015). Assessing the digital divide status of the Jordanian telecentre. *International Journal of Communications, Network and System Sciences*, 8(11), 428-439.

Almajali, D., Masa'deh, R., & Al-Lozi, M. (2016). Determinants of the actual use of e-learning systems: An empirical study on Zarqa University in Jordan. *Journal of Social Sciences (COES&RJ-JSS)*, 5(2), 172-200.

ALSarayreh, M., Jawabreh, O., ALkharabsheh, K., & Aldahamsheh, M. (2011). Tourism promotion through the Internet (websites) (Jordan as a case study). *Asian Social Science*, 7(6), [doi:10.5539/ass.v7n6p125](https://doi.org/10.5539/ass.v7n6p125).

Al-Shawagfih, K., Alananzeh, O., & Jawabreh, O. (2015). The foundations of selecting cultural tourism product in Jordan. *European Scientific Journal*, 11(29).

Altamony, H., & Gharaibeh, A. (2017). The role of academic researcher to Mintzberg's managerial roles. *International Journal of Business Management and Economic Research*, 8(2), 920-925.

Amyan, M., & Jawabreh, O. (2011). Mutual impact between tourism and the host community (a case study of Wadi Rum. *European Journal of Social Sciences*, 19(1).

Anja Heikkinen, (1997). Vocational education as a "life-project"? Reflections from the case of Finland. *Journal of European Industrial Training*, 21(6/7), 213-219.

Ardith Maney, (2012). Assisting workforce education in the Republic of Georgia, in Alexander W. Wiseman, Audree Chase-Mayoral, Thomas Janis, AnuSachdev (ed.) *Community Colleges Worldwide: Investigating the Global Phenomenon (International Perspectives on Education and Society, Volume 17)* Emerald Group Publishing Limited, pp.153-181.

Bazazo, I., Alshatnawi, E., Abdul Raheem, Jawabreh, O., & Alshawagfih, K. (2017). The effect of adopting the international standard (ISO 10015) in training programs on the performance quality of the workers at the Jordanian ministry of tourism and antiquities. *Journal of Social Sciences (COES&RJ-JSS)*, 6(3), 694-708, <https://doi.org/10.25255/jss.2017.6.3.694.708>.

Christine, V., & Tom, C. (2000). Students' perspectives of workplace learning and training in vocational education. *Education + Training*, 42(2), 83-92.

Durden, G.R., & Yang, G. (2006). Higher vocational education in China: a preliminary critical review of developments and issues in Liaoning province. *Journal of European Industrial Training*, 30(8), 622-638, <https://doi.org/10.1108/03090590610712287>

Felix, R. (2008). European vocational education and training: a prerequisite for mobility?. *Journal of European Industrial Training*, 32(2/3), 85-98, <https://doi.org/10.1108/03090590810861640>.

Irina Vasilyevna Terentyeva, Olga Kirillova, Tatyana Kirillova, Natalya Pugacheva, AleksandrLunev, Irina Chemerilova, & Anastasia Luchinina, (2018). Arrangement of cooperation between labour market and regional vocational education system. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 32(6), 1041-1055, <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJEM-10-2017-0296>.

Jacky & Lumby, (2000). Restructuring vocational education in Hong Kong. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 14(1), 16-23, <https://doi.org/10.1108/09513540010310369>.

Jawabreh, O. (2014). The impact of customer relationship marketing by Aqaba economic zone "A case study of five stars hotels". *International Journal of Academic Research in Accounting, Finance and Management Sciences*, 4(1), <http://dx.doi.org/10.6007/IJARAFMS/v4-i1/583>.

Jawabreh, O. (2017a). Analyzing factors affect on five stars occupational safety in Aqaba special economic zone authority (ASEZA). *Journal of Social Sciences (COES&RJ-JSS)*, 6(4), 802-815, <https://doi.org/10.25255/jss.2017.6.4.802.815>.

Impendent of the study of vocational education in vocational secondary schools....

Jawabreh, O. (2017b). Distinction of Jordan as a destination for religious tourism. *Journal of Environmental Management and Tourism*, 6(22), 1171-1182. [https://doi.org/10.14505/jemt.v8.6\(22\).03](https://doi.org/10.14505/jemt.v8.6(22).03).

Jawabreh, O. (2017c). An exploratory study of the motives of Jordanian out bound tourism and its impact on the development of tourism in Jordan. *International Journal of Applied Business and Economic Research*, 15(19 Part-II), 443-467.

Jawabreh, O., & Al Sarayreh, M. (2017). Analysis of job satisfaction in the hotel industry: a study of hotels five- Stars in Aqaba special economic zone authority (AZEZA). *International Journal of Applied Business and Economic Research*, 15 (19 Part-II), 389.

Jawabreh, O., Alananzeh, O., & Shatnawi, H. (2015). Managing tourism effects for attitudes of Jordanians towards tourism: the case of Petra. *European Journal of Social Sciences*, 48(1).

Jawabreh, O., Al Jaffal, T., Abdelrazaq, H., & Mahmoud, R. (2018). The impact of menus on the customer satisfaction in restaurants classified in Aqaba special economic zone authority (ASEZA). *Journal of Tourism, Hospitality and Sports*, 33.

Jawabreh, O. Bushra, A., Ismail, A., & Qatada, A. (2017). Assessing factors that prevent female students from studying hotel management: A case study of the University of Jordan (Aqaba branch). *Journal of Management Research*, 9(4), <https://doi.org/10.5296/jmr.v9i4.11690>

Jeremy, R., Huyton, & Anthony Ingold, (1999). A commentary by Chinese hotel workers on the value of vocational education. *Journal of European Industrial Training*, 23(1), 16-24, <https://doi.org/10.1108/03090599910253492>.

Karajeh, H., & Maqableh, M. (2014). Security of cloud computing environment. The 23rd IBIMA Conference on Vision 2020: Sustainable Growth, Economic Development, and Global Competitiveness, USA, 2202-2215.

Kateb, M., Swies, R., Obeidat, B., & Maqableh, M. (2015). An investigation on the critical factors of information system implementation in Jordanian information technology companies. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 7(36), 11-28.

Kenneth, S. (1976). Vocational guidance and promotion in West Germany. *Industrial and Commercial Training*, 8(1), 22-26, <https://doi.org/10.1108/eb003517>.

Khwaldeh, S., Al-Hadid, I., Masa'deh, R., & Alrowwad, A. (2017). The association between e-services web portals information quality and ICT competence in the Jordanian universities. *Asian Social Science*, 13(3), 156-169.

Lam, M.Y., Gary, K.K., & Poon, K.S. (2008). An organizational learning model for vocational education in the context of TQM culture. *International Journal of Quality & Reliability Management*, 25(3), 238-255, <https://doi.org/10.1108/02656710810854269>.

Lee, S.F., Lo, K.K., Leung, F., & OnKo, A. (2000). Strategy formulation framework for vocational education: integrating SWOT analysis, balanced scorecard, QFD methodology and MBNQA

education criteria. *Managerial Auditing Journal*, 15(8), 407-423, <https://doi.org/10.1108/02686900010353999>.

Lenita, H., & Taina, J. (2015). Contextualizing entrepreneurial learning in basic and vocational education. *Journal of Enterprising Communities: People and Places in the Global Economy*, 9(1), 45-60, <https://doi.org/10.1108/JEC-03-2013-0006>.

Liza, R., Kristinn, H., & Christian, I. (2015). Gender segregation in vocational education: Introduction, in Christian Imdorf, Kristinn Hegna, Liza Reisel (ed.) *Gender Segregation in Vocational Education (Comparative Social Research, Volume 31)* Emerald Group Publishing Limited, pp. 1-22.

Marlise, K. (2010). Job or further training?: Impact of the Swiss basic federal Vocational Education and Training (VET) certificate on the careers of low achieving young people. *Education + Training*, 52(5), 391-403, <https://doi.org/10.1108/00400911011058334>.

Martin, G. (1997). Planning for vocational education, training and employment: a minimalist approach. *International Journal of Manpower*, 18(1/2), 206-227, <https://doi.org/10.1108/01437729710169346>.

Martinus, S. (1997). Regional development and the tasks of vocational education and training professionals. *Journal of European Industrial Training*, 21(6/7), 229-237, <https://doi.org/10.1108/03090599710171549>.

Maqableh, M., & Karajeh, H. (2014). Job scheduling for cloud computing using neural networks. *Communications and Network*, 6(3), 191-200.

Maqableh, M., Rajab, L., Quteshat, W., Khatib, T., & Karajeh, H. (2015). The impact of social media networks websites usage on students' academic performance. *Communications and Network*, 7(4), 159-171.

Masa'deh, R. (2016a). The role of knowledge management infrastructure in enhancing job satisfaction at Aqaba five star hotels in Jordan. *Communications and Network*, 8(4), 219-240.

Masa'deh, R. (2016b). The role of emotional intelligence in enhancing organizational effectiveness: the case of information technology managers in Jordan. *International Journal of Communications, Network and System Sciences*, 9(6), 234-249.

Masa'deh, R., Almajali, D., Alrowwad, A., & Obeidat, B. (2019a). The role of knowledge management infrastructure in enhancing job satisfaction: a developing country perspective. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Information, Knowledge, and Management*, 14, 1-25.

Masa'deh, R., Gharaibeh, A., Maqableh, M., & Karajeh, H. (2013a). An empirical study of antecedents and outcomes of knowledge sharing capability in Jordanian telecommunication firms: a structural equation modeling approach. *Life Science Journal*, 10(4), 2284-2296.

Masa'deh, R., Hunaiti, Z., & Bani Yaseen, A. (2008). An integrative model linking IT-business strategic alignment and firm performance: the mediating role of pursuing innovation and

Impendent of the study of vocational education in vocational secondary schools....

knowledge management strategies. *Communications of the International Business Information Management Association (IBIMA) Journal*.

Masa'deh, R., Obeidat, B., Maqableh, M., & Shah, M. (2019b). The impact of business intelligence systems on an organization's effectiveness: the role of metadata quality from a developing country's view. *International Journal of Hospitality & Tourism Administration*, Forthcoming.

Masa'deh, R., Shannak, R., & Maqableh, M. (2013b). A structural equation modeling approach for determining antecedents and outcomes of students' attitude toward mobile commerce adoption. *Life Science Journal*, 10(4), 2321-2333.

Mike, P., & Dimitrios, B. (2004). Family hotel businesses: strategic planning and the need for education and training. *Education + Training*, 46(8/9), 406-415.

Mike, Rimmington, (1999). Vocational education: challenges for hospitality management in the new millennium. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 11(4), 186-192, <https://doi.org/10.1108/09596119910263595>.

Mikkawi, B., & Al-Lozi, M. (2017). The impact of knowledge management infrastructure on academic staff effectiveness: an empirical study at The University of Jordan. *Jordan Journal of Business Administration*, 13(1), 95-127.

Nick, Johns, & Mike McKechnie, (1995). Career demands and learning perceptions of hotel and catering graduates – ten years on. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 7(5), 9-12, <https://doi.org/10.1108/09596119510090717>.

Nikitas P., & Dimitris, S. (1997). The development of vocational education policy in Greece: a critical approach. *Journal of European Industrial Training*, 21(6/7), 192-202, <https://doi.org/10.1108/03090599710171503>.

Obeidat, B., Tarhini, A., & Aqqad, N. (2017). The impact of intellectual capital on innovation via the mediating role of knowledge management: a structural equation modeling approach. *International Journal of Knowledge Management Studies*, 8(3/4), 273-298.

Obeidat, O., Tarhini, A., & Aqqad, N. (2019). The relationship among emotional intelligence, conflict management styles, and job performance in Jordanian banks. *International Journal of Human Resources Development and Management*, Forthcoming.

Petya, I., Rumiana, S., & Pepka, B. (2015). Regional gender differences in vocational education in Bulgaria, in Christian Imdorf, Kristinn Hegna, Liza Reisel (ed.) *Gender Segregation in Vocational Education (Comparative Social Research, Volume 31)* Emerald Group Publishing Limited, pp.151-180.

Qusay, Q., Jawabreh, O., Bashar, M., & Rami, M. (2018). Why Arab societies do not encourage the work of their members in hotels?, *Modern Applied Science*, 12(11), <https://doi.org/10.5539/mas.v12n11p259>.

Ray & Thorogood, (1982). Current themes in vocational education and training policies: part 1". *Industrial and Commercial Training*, 14(10), 328-331, <https://doi.org/10.1108/eb003908>.

Richard, N.S., Robinson, A., Solnet, D., Goh, E., & Victor J. Callan, (2016). Attitudinal similarities and differences of hotel frontline occupations. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 28(5), 1051-1072, <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJCHM-08-2014-0391>.

Sheu, Hua Chen, Hung Tso Lin, & Hong Tau Lee, (2004). Enterprise partner selection for vocational education: analytical network process approach. *International Journal of Manpower*, 25(7), 643-655, <https://doi.org/10.1108/01437720410563980>.

Simon, Chak-keung Wong, & Jane Shiyin Li, (2015). Will hotel employees' perception of unethical managerial behavior affect their job satisfaction?: a study of Chinese hotel employees in China. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 27(5), 853-877, <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJCHM-06-2013-0253>.

Simon, F., & Megginson, D. (1996). Competence-based vocational training: ten years on and still down the wrong path?. *Education + Training*, 38(3), 17-27, <https://doi.org/10.1108/00400919610117380>.

Tarhini, A., Alalwan, A., Al-Qirim, N., & Algharabat, R. (2018). An analysis of the factors influencing the adoption of online shopping. *International Journal of Technology Diffusion (IJTD)*, 9(3), 68-87.

Tarhini, A., Al-Badi, A., Almajali, M., & Alrabayaah, S. (2017a). Factors influencing employees' intention to use cloud computing. *Journal of Management and Strategy*, 8(2), 47.

Tarhini, A., Al-Busaidi, K., Bany Mohammed, A., & Maqableh, M. (2017b). Factors influencing students' adoption of e-learning: a structural equation modeling approach. *Journal of International Education in Business*, 10(2), 164-182.

Tarhini, A., Bany Mohammed, A., & Maqableh, M. (2016). Modeling factors affecting student's usage behaviour of e-learning systems in Lebanon. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 11(2), 299.

Tarhini, A., Mgbemena, C., & Trab, MSA. (2015). User adoption of online banking in Nigeria: a qualitative study. *Journal of Internet Banking and Commerce*, 20(3), 1-8.

Yana, van der Meulen Rodgers, & Teresa Boyer, (2006). Gender and racial differences in vocational education: an international perspective. *International Journal of Manpower*, 27(4), 308-320, <https://doi.org/10.1108/01437720610679188>.

Yassien, E., & Mufleh, M. (2017). The impact of ERP system's usability on enterprise resource planning project implementation success via the mediating role of user satisfaction. *Journal of Management Research*, 9(3), 49-71.